

1 **Table S1 The List Primer sequence of mRNA**

Number	Primer	Primer sequence (5' to 3')
1	mMir27b-F	CGCCTTGTGGCTCTTTGGAAA
2	mMir27b-R	TGACAACACAGCCTTGAGGCAG
3	IL-1b-F	TTACAGTGGCAATGAGGATGAC
4	IL-1b-R	GTCGGAGATTTCGTAGCTGGAT
5	Fgf1-F	CCCTGACCGAGAGGTTCAAC
6	Fgf1-R	GTCCCTTGTCCCATCCACG
7	Grm1-F	TGGAACAGAGCATTGAGTTCATC
8	Grm1-R	CAATAGGCTTCTTAGTCCTGCC
9	Ndufs4-F	CTGCCGTTTCCGTCTGTAGAG
10	Ndufs4-R	TGTTATTGCGAGCAGGAACAAA
11	Pkia-F	AGACAGAAGGTGAAGATGATGG
12	Pkia-R	AGCAATGCCAGGAGATTCG
13	Ech1-F	GCTACCGCGATGACAGTTTC
14	Ech1-R	TCAGAGATCGAAGGCTGATGTT
15	Dram2-F	GCTGTCTTGCCTTTAGTATGG
16	Dram2-R	AGATAACCAACAGTAGTCGGACC
17	Eepd1-F	GGCTGCCATCGCTCTATCC
18	Eepd1-R	GGCTGCCATCGCTCTATCC
19	Tmem135-F	TCCCCTCTGCGTTTAGGCA
20	Tmem135-R	GGGCATGGTGGATTCTGTGT
21	Opa1-F	TGGAAAATGGTTCGAGAGTCAG
22	Opa1-R	CATTCCGCTCTAGGTTAAAGCG
23	Crebrf-F	AGCGTAAGCGGAATGGACC
24	Crebrf-R	CAGGACATCTGTGAAAGTCTCC
25	Stard7-F	ACCAGTACCGAGTTTTTGGAAC
26	Stard7-R	GAACCTCAGAACCACTAACAGC
27	Cth-F	TTCTGCCTAGTTCCAGCAT
28	Cth-R	GGAAGTCCTGCTTAAATGTGGTG
29	Tmbim6-F	TCCCACATAACTCCCTCGACA
30	Tmbim6-R	GTGTGTGACCACATGGACATAG
31	Aldh5a1-F	CGGTCAAGGAGAGGAGCTTAC
32	Aldh5a1-R	GGACTAGCCCTCGTTATCTTT
33	Neurl4-F	TACGCACATGGCCTCGTTTT
34	Neurl4-R	CCCATCACGCCTCACTTCA
35	Nrbf2-F	AAGGACCCCTCAACCTTGCT
36	Nrbf2-R	AAGGACCCCTCAACCTTGCT
37	Hspd1-F	CACAGTCCTTCGCCAGATGAG
38	Hspd1-R	CTACACCTTGAAGCATTAAAGGCT
39	ANP-F	GCTTCCAGGCCATATTGGAG
40	ANP-R	GGGGGCATGACCTCATCTT
41	BNP-F	GAGGTCACTCCTATCCTCTGG
42	BNP-R	GCCATTTCTCCGACTTTTCTC
43	Pparg1a-F	TATGGAGTGACATAGAGTGTGCT
44	Pparg1a-R	CCACTTCAATCCACCCAGAAAAG
45	GAPDH-F	AGGTCCGGTGTGAACGGATTTG
46	GAPDH-R	TGTAGACCATGTAGTTGAGGTCA
47	SKA-F	CCCAAAGCTAACCGGGAGAAG
48	SKA-R	CCAGAATCCAACACGATGCC

2 **The List sequence of miRNA**

1	miR27b-mimic	UUCACAGUGGCUAAGUUCUGC
2	miR27b-inhibitor	CGUCUUGAAUCGGUGACACUU

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1 Regents or kits included Sirius red (Solarbio, Catalog: G1470, Beijing, China), miR-
2 27b-3p mimic (Ribobio, Catalog: 61743, Guangzhou, China), mimic-NC (Ribobio
3 Catalog: 61744,), miR-27b-3p inhibitor (Ribobio, Catalog: 80613), inhibitor-
4 NC(Ribobio, Catalog: 80615), Lipofectamine 3000 reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
5 Catalog: L3000015, Boston, Massachusetts, USA), DAB (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
6 Catalog: 34002), Opti-MEM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Catalog:31985062,), si-
7 FGFR1(Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Catalog: sc-29317, Texas ,USA), control si-
8 RNA(Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Catalog: sc-37007) , isoflurane (RWD Life Science,
9 Catalog: R510-22, Shenzhen, China), AngII (Sigma-Aldrich, Catalog: 05-23-0101,
10 Darmstadt, Germany), ISO (Sigma-Aldrich, Catalog: 1351005), DMEM (Thermo
11 Fisher Scientific, Catalog: A4192101), Pentobarbital (Sigma-Aldrich, Catalog: P3761,
12 Darmstadt, Germany), FBS (Gibco Life Technologies, Catalog: 10082147,
13 Gaithersburg, MD, USA), WGA (CytoFlamma, Catalog: RCS113, Korea), Neonatal
14 Heart Dissociation Kit (MACS, Catalog:130-098-373, Germany), Cardiac Myocyte
15 Medium (Cell Biologics, Catalog: M1263, Chicago, USA), Mito Stress Test Kit
16 (Agilent Technologies, Catalog:103015-100, California, USA), FGF1 ELISA kits (Bio-
17 Techne, Catalog: DY4686-05, Minnesota, USA), BrdU (Selleck Chemicals, Catalog:
18 S791895, Texas, USA). Antibodies included BNP (abcam, Catalog: ab19645,
19 Cambridge Science Park, UK), ANP32E (abcam, Catalog: ab5993), FGF1 (abcam,
20 Catalog: ab207321), Smad3 (Cell Signaling Technology CST, Catalog: #9523),
21 Phospho-Smad3 (CST, Catalog: #9520), GAPDH (Zhong Shan Golden Bridge ZSGB,
22 Catalog: TA309157, Beijing, China), PGC1 α (abcam, Catalog: ab54481), PGC1 β
23 (abcam, Catalog: ab176328), FGFR1 (abcam, Catalog: ab206328), Mac-2(Santa Cruz
24 Biotechnology, Catalog: sc-32790, Texas ,USA), IL-1 β (abcam, Catalog: ab9722), NF-
25 κ B p65 (abcam, Catalog:ab19870).